

Expanding Organization Consciousness: Key to resilience in today's environment

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Abstract

How can organizations survive and navigate in today business environment that is complex, dynamic and uncertain? They need to become more flexible, adaptable and willing to learn new emerging rules of the game. Accordingly leaders instead of pursuing detailed goals and increasing control, need to focus on increasing their awareness with respect to their behavior as well as the way their organization behaves.

Time pressure and daily problems bring leader's focus to now rather than dreaming about future plans. In this situation, the organization automatically becomes aware of itself and its surrounding; Awareness that is achieved through observation is heavily dependent on leaders and organization's consciousness. Now the question is how in practice we can increase organization and leader consciousness.

Today we look at organizations as living species with quantum behavior such as self-awareness, uniqueness, emergent, unpredictable, etc. Knowing a human being (with quantum nature) is impossible from outside and similarly gaining complete knowledge about an organization from outside is questionable.

This paper proposes a model to increase consciousness and awareness about an organization.

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Keywords: self awareness, organization ego, observation method, organization consciousness;

1. Introduction

Today we look at organizations as living species with quantum behavior such as self-awareness, uniqueness, emergent, unpredictable, etc. Knowing a human being (with quantum nature) is impossible from outside and similarly gaining complete knowledge about an organization from outside is questionable.

This paper proposes a model to increase consciousness and awareness about an organization.

2. Self knowledge

2.1. Selecting a technique to increase knowledge about oneself

There are different ways of meditating and increasing knowledge about oneself. Each method has its benefits and limitations. In our experience the method that is not very abstract and simpler is easier to apply in real environments like organizations. We suggest self-observation as a good method. It's a method without a detailed technique, can be applied easily and does not require theoretical knowledge, it's compatible with any religious belief and can be practiced anywhere and anytime but it's a slow and gradual process with no end. It requires consistency and patience. It emphasizes more on quality and identification of self-centered thoughts and full presence. It requires

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awareness about events happening inside and outside and accepting without judgment. It's a method that sounds very simple but not easy.

2.2. Outcome of self-knowledge is knowing the current situation

The outcome of awareness is gaining knowledge about current situation of oneself. However awareness by itself does not increase our self-consciousness, it is the first step of the process. Gaining the ability to know true self requires practice and time, it's a gradual process.

2.3. What we see at first?

In the initial steps we gain awareness about outer and more obvious layers of oneself or organization. Acceptance of these layers (that are more objective) is easier and our mind does not get too judgmental. It points to the tip of the iceberg. This kind of knowledge can be applied to organization, for example gaining knowledge about Dosha or blood group (which will be discussed in this paper) falls under this category.

2.4. Ego is the main obstacle towards gaining self-awareness

Ego interprets concepts and events and looks for meaning for them. In reality it's protecting itself by relating the cause of failure to outside (other people or the environment). It works on an unconscious level and it is very difficult to see its deeper levels. Ego is an obstacle towards self-awareness. We will discuss some of the better known mechanisms by which ego gets involved in coming up with meanings and interpretations.

2.5. Why someone/organization starts observing itself?

As discussed before the way towards increasing self-awareness requires consistency, high level of self-discipline and dedication and most of these changes are painful in the beginning. Now the question is how a person/organization gains the courage to see itself in the mirror. In our opinion there are three situations in which this happens:

- When there is benefit for the person/organization
- When the person/organization realizes that the reason for his problems lies in himself
- When the person/organization is worried about consequences of mistakes in the future

2.6. Results of applying these techniques in Academy of Quantum and Mysticism studies

Since 2010 these different Concepts has been taught to managers as part of MBA courses as Personal Development Course (by Dr.Imanirad) that has brought lasting improvements in their lives and organizations.

2.7. Complete self-observation

Complete self-awareness happens when we have peace of mind and the person is ready to accept the thing in the mirror. At this level of awareness the person goes beyond reacting to the environment and instead has an impact on it. As long as the person/organization is in this condition there is no need to make decisions and the path reveals itself along the way.

3. Organizational self-knowledge

Two basic elements that increase organizational self-knowledge are current awareness within the organization culture and leaders' awareness; Collective awareness of all employees is the basis of current awareness in organization culture. Leaders' awareness is also the collective awareness of the leaders of the organization. These two interact elements interact with each other and needed in order to increase organizational self-awareness. In the following pages we focus of the building blocks of leaders/organization behavior, conations and ego.

3.1. Basic categories of leader behaviors and organization culture

In this section we use metaphors adopted from ancient medical practice of Avicenna, Ayurveda and the more recent blood type grouping to propose some basic categories in leaders behavior and organization culture.

3.1.1. Avicenna: Four Humors and Temperaments

Avicenna theory is based on ancient Greek, Indian and Persian medical methods. In these methods the basic character of matter was extended to human beings.

As per Avicenna the four humors which fill the human body are: Choleric, Sanguine, Phlegm and Sediment and that correspond to fire, air, water and earth. Below chart shows these four categories and how they relate to each other:

Table 1. Four Temperaments characteristics

Temperament	Elements	Type
Choleric	Fire	Hot and Dry
Sanguine	Air	Hot and Wet
Phlegm	Water	Cold and Wet
Sediment	Earth	Cold and Dry

Depending on which element is more dominant in a person/organization, different Temperaments can become more dominant:

- If fire is the dominant element, the Temperament is hot and dry.
- If air is the dominant element, the Temperament is hot and wet.
- If water is the dominant elements, the Temperament becomes cold and wet.
- If earth is the dominant element, the Temperament becomes cold and dry.
- Some people have a balance of all the four elements and their Temperament becomes balanced.

Accordingly each person/organization has an intrinsic body temperature and humidity that is called dominant Temperament.

3.1.2. Dosha

Based on Ayurveda, ancient Indian medicine dating back to 5000 years ago, our physical body is a gate to our "Quantum mechanic body". This "Quantum mechanic body" is the basis of everything we are (whether tangible or intangible).

According to Ayurveda, the world is composed of five basic elements which can also be called as five basic energy frequencies which are fire, air, water, earth and ether.

Every phenomenon in mind produces a similar phenomenon in body. Ayurveda says this conversion happens in a point which is under the control of one of the three basic Doshas. Three main Doshas are called: Kapha, Pitta and Vata. Each Dosha is connected with two element; Kapha with water and earth, Pitta with fire and water and Vata with air and ether. See below table for characteristic of each Dosha:

Table 2. Three Doshas Characteristics

Vata	Pitta	Kapha
Dry	Sharp	Slow
Changeable	Hot	Cold
Moving	Light	Heavy
Quick	Fluid	Steady
Subtle	Moist	Sticky

Vata is characterized by tendency to change, Pitta with sharpness and Kapha with being a free spirit. By knowing a person/organization’s Dosha we can get answer to many questions about their behavior.

3.1.3. Blood type

According to some recent research, knowledge about our blood type is key factor in understanding ourselves. Blood type also determines characteristics such vulnerability to certain illnesses and also the type of food and sport activities that benefit our body the most. It also helps us to understand our capacity to burn certain calories and reaction to mental pressure.

We can also extend this metaphor to organization.

3.1.4. Correlation between Temperaments, Dosha and blood type

This type of research is in early stages and further focus and research is needed in this area. Highlights of some of the latest findings relevant to our discussion are as follows:

- It seems that in ancient times all human beings had O blood type. Gradually other blood types like A, then B and eventually AB come to existence.
- People with positive blood types are generally healthier from a nervous system perspective compared to people with negative blood type. Proper diet is different between positive and negative blood types and generally people with negative blood type are more nervous compared to positive blood types.
- O blood type seems to be the prevalent blood type and A, B is rarer among human beings.
- From a Temperament perspective, O and AB blood types are warm and A & B are cold.

Below table summarizes Temperaments, blood types and Dosha characteristics into 9 groups:

Table 3. Comparative Table

Blood type	Dosha	Temperament	Type
AB+	Vata-Pitta	Choleric	Hot and Dry
O+	Pitta	Sanguine	Hot and Wet
B+	Kapha	Phlegm	Cold and Wet
A+, A-, AB-, O-, B-	Vata-Kapha	Sediment	Cold and Dry
All	Three Dosha	Balanced	Balanced
All	Pitta-Vata	Sanguine-Choleric	Hot
All	Kapha-Pitta or Pitta-Kapha	Phlegm-Sanguine	Wet
All	Kapha-Vata	Phlegm-Sediment	Cold
All	Vata	Sediment-Choleric	Dry

We can extend this metaphor to organization culture as well.

3.2. Quotients of leaders and organizations

3.2.1. Physical Quotient (PQ)

Physical quotient is something that most of us are naturally aware of it but don't pay attention to. Our body does a lot of activities without our conscious effort like heart pumping blood in the body, nervous system mechanism, etc. People are different in terms of PQ. Professional athletes usually have a high level of PQ. People with high PQ are usually aware of the signs in their body, for example they can sense hunger and or fullness not from their mind pulses but from their body reaction. These people can feel the signs of sickness before becoming sick. People with high level of PQ have balanced weight, good diet and take good care of their body. All of this is possible when mind is in harmony with body.

PQ in organization can be represented with quickness in responding to changes in the environment, proper understanding of the real organization needs and also effort to create balance.

3.2.2. Intelligence Quotient (IQ)

The concept of IQ test started in France and became popular in the US in early 20th century to determine the IQ of American kids. IQ mainly measures someone ability in applying logic, work with numbers, identify similarities and imaginative skills. IQ is usually a representation of logic in a person and left side of brain.

In case of organization, IQ can be represented by the amount of scientific work and R&D, capacity to analyze and apply logic.

3.2.3. Emotional Quotient (EQ)

In a nutshell EQ is the ability to understand and manage oneself and others emotions which results in establishing positive and lasting relationships with others. It helps people to become aware of their emotions and manage them better. It also enables the person to become aware of other people's emotions, comprehend them and properly respond to them. EQ is grouped into four skills: (1) Knowledge of oneself emotions, (2) Management of ones emotions, (3) Knowledge of others emotions, (4) Management of others emotions.

For organizations EQ can be represented by its ability to build lasting relationship within itself as well as with the environment and customers.

3.2.4. Spiritual Quotient (SQ)

PQ helps person to have a healthy body and better connection between body and mind. IQ helps to think and decide logically. EQ helps to become aware of emotions and environment.

SQ enables the person to accept and adapt to the environment. It was introduced in 1997 by Danah Zohar. SQ affects other quotients and can lead them.

SQ in organization is represented by the ability to accept and adapt with itself (in general), with other organizations and customers. Capacity to use intuition is the result of this quotient.

3.3. Leaders and Organizations Conation

According to Kathy Kolbe, conation is the faculty of brain that drives you to take purposeful actions based on your instincts. Conative abilities are natural, inherent and unchanging talents that, when acted on, lead to success and well being as you use your creative energy to solve problems.

3.3.1. Kolbe index

Kolbe Index points to the underlying reason for behaviour and basically states that instead of controlling or ignoring conation the person should use its power.

3.3.2. Kolbe four types

According to Kolbe there are four types of intuitive techniques that people use to come up with innovative solutions. These intuitions are very hard to measure but the behavior stemming from them is easily identifiable. These main behavioral characteristics are as follows:

3.3.2.1. Fact Finder

This is the instinctive way we gather and share information. The person solves problems even without all the information pieces and can reduce complex problems into basic and simple concepts.

They don't do anything unless they read every direction carefully. This mode deals with detail and complexity, seeking to be both objective and appropriate. It is through the Fact Finder mode that you are a pragmatist, prober, arbitrator, practitioner, researcher, judge or realist.

3.3.2.2. Follow Thru

It is the instinctive by which we design and organize. The person finishes the job amid facing disagreements and resistance and makes sure the process/system.

Methodical and systematic, this mode is focused and structured and brings order and efficiency. People who lead with this mode are meticulous at planning, programming, designing and predictability is essential to their being. The instinct to pattern forces us into Follow Thru behaviour. It is through the Follow Thru mode that you are a planner, designer, regulator, pattern-maker, theorist and programmer.

3.3.2.3. Quick Start

This instinct leads us to action in uncertain and risky situations.

People who lead with this mode are deadline and crisis oriented. The instinct to innovate drives Quick Start energy. It is through the Quick Start mode that you are a catalyst, generalist, innovator, entrepreneur, promoter and improviser. Targeting your efforts through your strength in the Quick Start mode requires the freedom to:

Deviate, intuit, promote, invent, brainstorm, originate, change, challenge, contrive, risk, devise, abbreviate and experiment.

3.3.2.4. Implementer

It is the instinct that deals with the way we handle space and tangibles. For example it enables the person/organization to make a buy decision by visualizing the outcome.

Hands-on and craft-oriented, this mode brings tangible quality to actions. People who lead with this mode have a strong sense of three-dimensional form and substance and the ability to deal with the concrete. It is through the Implementer mode that you are builder, handcrafter, athlete, manufacturer, agriculturalist and artisan. Targeting your efforts through your strength in the Implementer mode requires the freedom to:

Craft, construct, master, build, repair, display, mould, practice, render, shape, form, use physical effort, demonstrate and put together.

3.4. Ego in leaders and organizations

What is ego? How it develops?

In simple words what we call ego refers to a mental perspective that has the ability to distort perception and feeling of a person/organization towards the world and eventually distort thinking and behavior. Presence of a big ego makes the person to believe that he is separate and different from others. Ego can develop within the leaders of the organization and spread through culture in the organization.

Some signs of its presence are self centered thoughts and narcissism. Our parents, school and society all play a role in our ego development but we're ultimately responsible to recognize it within ourselves.

In the following we have summarized some of the obvious signs and mechanisms ego:

3.4.1. Comparison

An inflated ego makes the person/organization not to be happy with what it got and constantly looking for change. This kind of comparison makes people worry all the time and reduce their positive energy. When comparing people focus too much on others achievements and forget about theirs and lose the sense of order.

3.4.2. Illusion

A big ego distorts perception of reality and brings a sense of illusion. The person won't be in touch with reality and see himself/herself as involved in everything. In this situation, the "I" is so big that it becomes the center of everything in thoughts. The person develops a sense of suspecting a hidden agenda in everything. Thoughts become polarized and everything and everyone is either with or against him/her. Ego eventually brings illusion in relationships as well. Feelings like anger, fear and worriedness enter the person life.

3.4.3. Judgment

An ego centric person uses his illusions to come to conclusion and judgment. Judgmental thinking negatively affects relationships. This makes the person extremely sensitive to other people judgment as well. Others acceptance of one's decisions becomes very important.

3.4.4. Labeling

One of the outcomes of judging is assigning good and bad labels to people, situations, events and organizations. The person sees everything either black or white. The person uses negative labels to justify his/her superiority.

3.4.5. Victory at all costs

Extreme competitiveness is one of the signs of a big ego. It means the effort to prove one's superiority over others at all costs. In this sort of competition only victory is important. Ego centric person only enjoys seeing himself as the winner and seeing other people's wins does not make him happy.

3.4.6. To lie

Lying is another technique that ego uses. For the ego centric person nothing is good enough and accordingly he/she is constantly hiding the reality and lying is one of the mechanisms of hiding it. Lying is not limited to verbal lies it also reflects in behavior as well. The person who lies sometimes plays unrealistic roles like too much care or courage that is not based on his/her true character. Telling the truth requires certain amount of courage which is not possible in the presence of ego.

3.4.7. *Wanting more*

Nothing is enough for ego and therefore nothing satisfies him/her. No amount superior to others. Wanting more makes people to start looking at others as mere tools. In this situation other people are good as long as they benefit the ego centric person. It eventually results in lack of peace in person's life. No amount of wealth or power can bring satisfaction. The person wants to be the winner all the time, the strongest person and also be seen is different and

3.4.8. *Show off*

As the ego centric person gets his motivations from outside, grabbing others attention becomes very important for him. They do anything to grab the attention of others. They're self confidence comes from other people praising them. To believe in themselves they need other people's approval.

3.4.9. *Humiliation*

Ego uses humiliation and looking down on other people including customers and competitors. As the person does not have self respect, it hides behind ego. This will negatively affect human relationships.

3.4.10. *Always being right or entitled*

The sense of always being right or entitled makes the person/organization to never apologize for his/her mistakes. The leaders can not tolerate complains from customers and employees.

3.4.11. *Controlling*

For the ego centric person other people's happiness is important but only the way they want it for them. These people usually become control freak in everything even the smallest details. This will result in weakening of leadership ability. He/she wants to make decision for everyone in every step of the process because he/she does not believes in other's judgment.

3.4.12. *Fake identity*

Everyone's true character comes from inside. As ego makes people that who they are is not enough, the person starts to search for identity which can be very different fro his/her true nature. The result makes the person to become dependent on this fake identity.

3.4.13. *Talking bad about other people*

Complaining about others gives a short satisfaction to the person which involves a feeling of superiority as it shows he knows more. The ego centric person thinks that the way to success is be blocking other people's success and complaining about them. The root cause of jealousy and complaining is usually not in knowing one's natural abilities.

3.4.14. *Complaining*

Ego stays alive by complaining. In extreme cases this process becomes automatic. This emotional pain makes ego stronger everyday.

4. Model of self-knowledge

The following model represents all the concepts discussed in this paper so far. A brief description of steps in this model will be discussed in the next page.

Figure 1. Model of self-knowledge

Steps of the model:

4.1. Self-knowledge and awareness of current situation

As mentioned before, leaders can use different methods to increase their self-knowledge. In parallel, there is a need to gain knowledge about organization culture (representing collective awareness of employees) using adapted

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methods. Only the organization can gain this knowledge and it's not possible through short term consulting process. In our opinion external consultants can only add true value if they are immersed in organization culture. Basically they need to become part of the organization and help leaders and employees to gain knowledge about themselves which is only possible in the long term when external consultant becomes a member of the organization.

4.2. Observation and monitoring

After leaders and organization become aware of the current situation (by applying above mentioned methods) it's the time to increase their self-awareness. Contemplation is a great tool in this respect. In the context of organization, business intelligence systems provide a good monitoring tool.

4.3. Expanding consciousness

In our opinion the key to survival in today's environment is expanding consciousness. This is only possible when we apply our understanding and knowledge and observe ourselves during making decisions and taking actions.

4.4. New balance state

New level of consciousness brings a new state of being (or balance state). Leaders need to understand this new level and eventually adapt to it.

4.5. Emergent decisions and strategies

Once leaders/organizations are in this new state, new paths start to emerge that entail emergent decisions. These decisions could become intuitive vs. analytical decisions. Since leaders have a new perspective they see new signs that will lead them to right decisions. One benefit is that leaders don't get stuck in paralysis and balance their analysis with intuition.

4.6. Experience and implementation

Once emergent strategy is implemented and leaders experience it, this will become a learning process.

4.7. Back to step 2

By going back to observation and monitoring step the feedback loop makes the process complete and whole which in due time creates new strategies based on continuous learning. This continues process of taking action and reflecting on it increase consciousness.

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